

Paper 10

ONLINE EDUCATION: A WAY FOR REALIZING THE DREAMS TO LEARN

Dr. Gaonkar Gopalakrishna M.¹ & Manjunath M.²

¹Associate Professor and Head, Department of Economics, Government First Grade College and Centre for PG Studies, Tenkanidiyoor, Udipi, Karantaka, India.

Email: gmgakonkar40@gmail.com

² Lecturer in Economics, Richard Almeida Memorial College, Navunda, Kundapur Taluk, Karnataka, India.

Email: golihole143@gmail.com

Abstract:

Online education is becoming a popular mode of imparting education to those who are in very need and thrust of learning new and advanced knowledge. Online teaching is gradually replacing the conventional class room methods of education because, E-learning or e-education programs can offer wider content on a topic than the conventional education lesson: in a conventional class the learners are limited to the amount of information that they can get but online education is a dynamic industry, with new technologies and instructional strategies always on the horizon. No doubt, Behaviorism, cognitivism, and constructivism are the three broad learning theories most often utilized in the creation of instructional environments. But, these theories were developed in a time when learning was not impacted through technology. With the progress in technology and the advancement in learning connectivism provides insight into learning skills. The paper tries to examine, the forms, plus points and shortcomings of online education. The main forms are Web-based learning, virtual classroom learning, learning **through** Mobile, Video-based Learning etc. Major plus points, convenient, cost effective, job oriented, etc, and a few short comings, lack of awareness, inadequate technology, language barriers, etc. are discussed in brief.

Keywords: Online Education, Internet, Learning, Skill and Connectivism.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the recent years, online education is becoming a popular mode of imparting education to those who are in very need and thrust of learning new and advanced knowledge. Online teaching is gradually replacing the conventional class room methods of education because, E-learning or e-education programs can offer wider content on a topic than the conventional education lesson. In a conventional class the learners are limited to the certain amount of information that they can get but online education is a dynamic industry, with new technologies and instructional strategies. But, the field of education has been slow to recognize both the impact

of new learning tools and the environmental changes in what it means to learn. The New Media Consortium's 2016 Horizon Report expects "increasing use of blended learning designs" to strongly impact online learning over the next two years (New Media Consortium, 2016). The Connectivism provides insight into learning skills and tasks needed for learners to flourish in a digital era. (George Siemens) In the light of the above views, the paper tries to examine, the forms and plus and minus of online education.

2. OBJECTIVES & METHODOLOGY

To study the forms of the online Education, To know the plus points of online education and to examine the shortcomings of online education. This study is purely a descriptive study, it is carried out with the help of available secondary data, published reports and research articles in journals and edited books.

3. MEANING OF ONLINE EDUCATION

E learning is an approach to teaching and learning, representing all or part of the educational model applied, that is based on the use of electronic media and devices as tools for improving access. The introduction of computers was the basis of this revolution and with the passage of time, as we get hooked to smartphones, tablets, etc, these devices now have an importance place in the classrooms for learning. Thus, E-learning involves the use of a computer or electronic device (e.g. a mobile phone) to provide training, educational or learning material (Derek Stockley 2003)

4. FORMS OF ONLINE EDUCATION:

As per the study, online education can be imparted in different ways. Here, it is tried to summarize a few among them. Computer-Based Training, CD-ROM Based Learning, Web-Based Learning, Virtual Classroom Learning, Learning through Mobile, Collective Learning, Video based learning, custom e learning, Off the shelf e learning, learning through webinars. Thus, above mentioned are a few e-Learning forms. Today a number of platforms are coming up to deliver E-education throughout the world. Example, MOOC, COURSERA, Etc.

5. PLUS POINTS OF ONLINE EDUCATION

Online education is realizing the dreams of learning or acquiring the knowledge of many people in the world. It carries a number of merits particularly in technically advanced country. Flexible Scheduling, means you can schedule your time according your free time or available time, so it is more convenient. Online learning saves money because no travelling cost, accommodation cost and more fees. It is easily affordable. Every individual learn according his face of learning, he is not suppose to depend on friends or peers in the process of his learning. This way of learning is best suits to job holders, they can fulfill their dream of learning and satisfy their hunger of knowledge, means pursue a Job along with Studies. Any one who have internet connection can easily access to learning materials, this is the biggest plus point learners. When there is no need to travel, no need to attend not important classes, learner can save lot of time. It can meet a specific learning objective, because the majority online courses are aim and outcome oriented. if the learner study a course with a specific objective, definitely he fulfills it.

Geographical distance, in online education, will not be the barrier to the learner, a person from any corner of the world, can access and earn knowledge without any problem. There are a number of self paced courses, there is no time bound to take the course thus, pursue study whenever, wherever. These courses reduce the cost of education to the possible level. No transport cost, no material cost, only examination fee, means, cost of getting education is bare minimum. Totally, it is in right sense possibilities of dream come true to a innumerable of education aspirants across the world.

6. SHORTCOMINGS OF ONLINE LEARNING

Online education is not free from minus points or shortcomings. Of course, to take any positive steps in the world, there is always some challenges. Here we bring forth some challenges in the field of online education. Majority in the world are not aware about these type of education, probably it may take several years to reach who are in need of it. There is insufficient digital infrastructure in many countries of the world. It is so because there is no proper internet connection, computers, power supply and other needy materials. In a class room condition teacher observes, motivates student on the base of students interest and attitude. In an online learning a lazy learner some time drop the course or not studies up to the mark because lack of motivation. Regarding the credibility of degree there is still ambiguity among people because a number of fraudulent courses are in operation, they do not have any credentials in their certificates. The biggest drawback of online learning is limited social interaction. Since online education can be accessed at home or any other convenient place, there is very limited direct interaction with the teacher and other people doing the course. Language of the course is another major barrier, for example :India is a multi-linguistic country, and a vast majority of the population comes from rural areas. They may not understand English, which is considered as world language. In such condition interested learners hesitate to take the course. Overdependence on technology can be a major drawback in online learning mode of education, especially when the learning takes place in an online environment. Any malfunctioning software or hardware can bring an ongoing class to a standstill and interrupt the learning process. Similarly, if a student is not computer and tech savvy, his learning experience can be dissatisfactory. Though the learner feels there is no much cost, in reality there are some hidden costs like purchasing computer, installing secured internet connection, need web camera, printer etc. Thus, online learning is not fully free from cost. Often considered to be the lesser cousin of regular education, online education is often plagued by lack of enough good quality faculty members. In other cases, even if the instructor is good, he or she may not be comfortable with teaching in an online environment. Sometimes the technology might not do full justice to the delivery and design of the course. A student loses out in all these scenarios. Online education providers should realize that it is not the technology, but good and effective teachers that teach students

7. SWING IN INDIAN ONLINE EDUCATION

Online education in India has been on an upward swing in the last few years and the trend is expected to continue in the days to come maybe at a much accelerated pace. There is an ever-growing population of education-hungry students & professionals in India that is going

online. Because there are 50 crore students in India falling in the age bracket of 5 - 24 years and the country is just not equipped to provide a decent education to such a huge number only through the traditional mode. i.e. classroom teaching. As per the statistics shared by COURSERA (world's largest open online education i.e. MOOC provider), there were 13 lakh online learners from India as compared to the total 180 lakh online learners on COURSERA. The Indian government aims to increase the enrollment (GER) in universities from 23% in 2014-15 to 30% by the year 2030. But, practically this is not easy by just setting up more traditional classrooms & universities. (The Learning House, 2016)

8. CONCLUSION

In recent years, books are gradually getting replaced by electronic educational materials like optical discs or pen drives. Knowledge can also be shared via the Internet, which is accessible anywhere, anytime means helps to satisfy the hunger of learning. Thus, though the online education has a number of challenges ahead to reach majority in the world, slowly and steadily will gain popularity and it will be useful to huge number of people on the globe.

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